

UPLC Method Development, Validation & Degradation Studies of Motixafortide Tablet dosage forms

S. Padmavathi¹, Pulagani Triveni²

¹Professor & HOD Department of pharmaceutical chemistry, Nirmala college of pharmacy, Atmakur, Mangalagiri, Guntur-522503.

²PG Research scholar, Nirmala college of pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical analysis, Nirmala College of Pharmacy, Atmakur, Mangala Giri, Guntur-522503

ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise, sensitive and reproducible reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) method has been developed for the quantitative analysis of Motixafortide in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation of Motixafortide was achieved on Waters Acquity, by using Agilent Eclipse plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1 μ m) column and the mobile phase containing Acetonitrile + 0.1% Formic acid in the ratio of 30:70% v/v. The flow rate was 0.5 ml/min; detection was carried out by absorption at 229nm using a photodiode array detector at ambient temperature. The number of theoretical plates and tailing factor for Motixafortide were NLT 2000 and should not more than 2 respectively. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas of all measurements always less than 2.0. The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines. The method was found to be simple, economical, suitable, precise, accurate & robust method for quantitative analysis of Motixafortide.

Keywords: UPLC, Motixafortide, method development, validation, Degradation studies.

INTRODUCTION

Chromatography is a method for separating a mixture's components, or solutes, based on how evenly each solute is dispersed between a stationary phase that is adjacent to the mobile phase, a moving fluid stream. While the stationary phase can either be a solid or a liquid, the mobile phase can either be a liquid or a gas. The factors that influence this separation are the molecular characteristics associated with adsorption, affinity, and partition, as well as variations among their molecular weights [1, 2]. As a result, certain components of the mixture travel quickly through the mobile phase and exit the chromatographic system, while others pass slowly through the stationary phase and spend more time there. Based on this methodology, the chromatography technique is composed of three elements.

- Stationary phase: A solid phase or a layer of liquid absorbed on the surface of solid support is always present in this phase.
- Separated molecules.
- Mobile phase: This phase typically contains a liquid or a gas component. [3]

An essential liquid chromatography (LC) method for separating various components in mixtures is high-performance liquid chromatography. It has been used for many years to quantify and identify compounds throughout the drug development process all over the globe. Column technology (column dimension and column particle size) and instrumentation have significantly advanced in order to further accomplish the substantial rise in sensitivity, resolution, and speed in LC [4]. Waters developed and patented Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) in 2004 to accomplish the aforementioned goals. UPLC is based on tiny, porous particles (sub 2micron

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

particles). The underlying theory of this development, which links the relationship between plate height and linear velocity, is the Van Deemter equation. Because the top pressure limit of traditional HPLCs is approximately 6000 psi, the tiny particles need a high pressure to function with UPLC. UPLC refers to Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography. It is a method of separating a mixture of components into individual components through a porous medium under the influence of the solvent. UPLC is a derivative of HPLC whose underlying principle is that as column packing particle size decreases, efficiency and thus resolution increases.

MATERIALS & METHOD:

DRUG PROFILE OF MOTIXAFORTIDE

Table no 1: charecteristic properties of motixafortide.

IUPAC name	(3 <i>S</i> ,6 <i>S</i> ,9 <i>S</i> ,12 <i>S</i> ,15 <i>R</i> ,20 <i>R</i> ,23 <i>S</i> ,26 <i>S</i> ,29 <i>S</i> ,32 <i>S</i>)-3,6-bis(4-aminobutyl)- <i>N</i> -[(2 <i>S</i>)-1-amino-5-carbamimidamido-1-oxopentan-2-yl]-15-[[[(2 <i>S</i>)-2-[[[(2 <i>S</i>)-5-carbamimidamido-2-[[[(2 <i>S</i>)-5-carbamimidamido-2-[(4-fluorobenzoyl)amino]pentanoyl]amino]pentanoyl]amino]-3-naphthalen-2-yl]propanoyl]amino]-26-(3-carbamimidamidopropyl)-9,23-bis[3-(carbamoylamino)propyl]-12,29-bis[(4-hydroxyphenyl)methyl]-2,5,8,11,14,22,25,28,31-nonaoxo-17,18-dithia-1,4,7,10,13,21,24,27,30-nonazabicyclo[30.3.0]pentatriacontane-20-carboxamide
Molecular Formula	C ₉₇ H ₁₄₄ FN ₃₃ O ₁₉ S ₂
Molecular Weight	2159.55 g/mol
Description	Motixafortide, marketed as Aphexda, is a hematopoietic stem cell mobilizer and CXCR4 antagonist used in combination with filgrastim to prepare patients with multiple myeloma for autologous stem cell transplantation by increasing the number of stem cells in the bloodstream.
Half life	The effective half-life of motixafortide in human plasma is approximately 2 hours.
Category	Motixafortide is a heterodetic cyclic peptide that has antineoplastic activity. It is a CXC chemokine receptor 4 (CXCR4) antagonist with an IC ₅₀ value of 0.8 nM and is currently under clinical investigation for the treatment of hematological malignancies, solid tumors, and stem cell mobilization.

TABLE NO: 2 Method: UPLC Method Development for Motixafortide: Optimum conditions.

S.No	Name	Model	Manufacturer
1.	UPLC	ACQUITY	Agilent1290 Infinity II LC System equipped with PDA- detector
2.	pH meter	pH700	Eutech
3.	Weighing balance	BSA224S-CW	Sartouris

4.	UV/VIS spectrophotometer	UV-1700	UV-1700
5.	Pipettes, beakers and Burettes	Class-A	Borosil
6.	Ultra sonicator	UCA 701	Unichrome
7.	Pump	Isocratic model	Waters

TABLE NO: 3 List of chemicals used in UPLC Method

S.No	Name	Grade	Manufacturer
1.	Acetonitrile	HPLC	Merck
2.	Water (Milli Q)	HPLC	In house production
3.	Tri fluoro acetic acid	AR	Merck
4.	Formic acid	AR	Merck

5.1 Determination of Working Wavelength (λ_{max}):

5.1 Determination of Working Wavelength (λ_{max}):

In the estimation of drug maximum absorbance was used. So this wavelength was used in the estimation to estimate Motixafortide drug accurately. The wavelength of maximum absorption of the solution of the drug in mixture of Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (30+70) were scanned using PDA Detector within the wavelength region of 200–400 nm against Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (30+70) as blank. The absorption curve shows isobestic point at 229nm. Thus 229 nm was selected as detector wavelength for the UPLC chromatographic method.

5.2 Chromatographic conditions:

During the selection of chromatographic conditions, numbers of trails were carried out and the best trail was selected for optimized method.

5.2.1 Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide working standard into a 10 ml volumetric flask add Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further pipette 1ml of the above stock solutions into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (100ppm of Motixafortide)

5.2.2 Sample Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10mL volumetric flask add Diluent and sonicate it up to 30 min to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further pipette 1 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. Then it is filtered through 0.22micron Injection filter. (100ppm of Motixafortide)

Fig:1 Isobestic points of Motixafortide

5.3 Trails in optimization of chromatographic condition:

Table No.4: TRIAL-1 Chromatographic conditions

Column	Phenomenox C18 (50x 1.7mm, 2.1 μ m)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile + 0.1% TFA (30+70)
Detection wavelength	200-400nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5 μ l
Run time	5min
Observation	Retention time is not within the limit

Table no 5 optimum conditions of UPLC

TRAILNO2 Fig No.2 Chromatogram of standard

Fig: 3 trail of the Motixafortide

	Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Motixafortide	2.012	1686737	1.26	2015

Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
Motixafortide	2.012	1686737	1.26	2015

Table No.7 TRIAL-4 Chromatographic conditions

Column	Phenomenox C18 (50x 1.7mm, 2.1µm)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile + 0.1% TFA (40+60)
Detection wavelength	229nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5µl
Run time	3.50min
Observation	Broad peak is observed

Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
Motixafortide	1.695	2612357	2.03	1865

Fig 5: TRIAL-8 Chromatographic conditions

Column	Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1µm)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile + 0.1% TFA (50+50)
Detection wavelength	229 nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5µl
Run time	10min
Observation	Unknown peaks are observed

Fig: 5of the Motixafortide

	Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Motixafortide	1.433	381506	1.41	1348

Table No.9: TRIAL-5 Chromatographic conditions

Column	Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1 μ m)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (10+90)
Detection wavelength	29nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5 μ l
Run time	10min
Observation	Peak shape is not good

	Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Motixafortide	1.162	4015263	2.12	2045

Table No.10: TRIAL-6 Chromatographic conditions

Column	Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1 μ m)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (20+80)
Detection wavelength	229 nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5 μ l
Run time	3min
Observation	Base line is not good

	Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Motixafortide	0.513	16895302	1.01	9236

Table No.11: TRIAL-7 Optimized Chromatographic conditions

Column	Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1 μ m)
Mobile phase ratio	Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (30+70)
Detection wavelength	229 nm
Flow rate	0.5ml/min
Injection volume	5 μ l
Run time	2min
Observation	This method is suitable for validation

Fig no 8 The Motixafortide peak was observed at 0.693 min with peak area 2745862, tailing factor 0.98. This trial was optimized.

	Name	RT	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Motixafortide	0.693	2745862	0.98	8756

General preparations

Preparation of 0.1% Formic acid buffer:

1ml of formic acid is dissolved in 1 litre of HPLC water and filtered through 0.22 μ membrane filter paper.

Preparation of Mobile Phase: Mobile phase was prepared by mixing Acetonitrile and 0.1% formic acid taken in the ratio 30:70. It was filtered through 0.22 μ membrane filter to remove the impurities which may interfere in the final chromatogram.

Chromatographic condition:

Use Agilent1290 Infinity II LC System equipped with PDA- detector.

Column : Agilent Eclipse Plus C18 (50x 4.6mm, 2.1µm)

Mobile phase ratio : Acetonitrile and 0.1% Formic acid (30+70)

Detection wavelength : 229 nm

Flow rate : 0.5ml/min

Injection volume : 5µl

Run time : 2min

Diluent: Acetonitrile.

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide working standard into a 10 ml volumetric flask add Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1ml of the above stock solutions into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (100ppm of Motixafortide)

Sample Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10mL volumetric flask add Diluent and sonicate it up to 30 min to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. Then it is filtered through 0.22 micron Injection filter. (100ppm of Motixafortid)

Procedure:

Inject 5 µL of the standard, sample into the chromatographic system and measure the areas for Motixafortide peak and calculate the %Assay by using the formulae.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

Tailing factor for the peak due to Motixafortide in Standard solution should not be more than 2.0

Theoretical plates for the Motixafortide peak in Standard solution should not be less than 2000.

Formula for Assay:

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{AT}{AS} * \frac{WS}{DS} * \frac{DT}{WT} * \frac{\text{Average weight}}{\text{Label Claim}} * \frac{P}{100} * 100$$

Where: AT = average area counts of test (sample) preparation.

AS = average area counts of standard preparation.

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg.

DS = Dilution of working standard in ml.

DT = Dilution of test (sample) in ml.

WT = Weight of test (sample) taken in mg.

P = Percentage purity of working standard

LC = Label Claim mg/ml.

METHOD VALIDATION SUMMARY:**Specificity:**

Specificity of an analytical method is ability to measure specifically the analyte of interest without interference from blank and known impurities. For this purpose blank chromatogram, standard chromatogram and sample chromatogram were recorded. The chromatogram of blank shows no response at the retention times of drugs which confirms the response of drug was specific.

Fig no 9 Blank chromatogram

System Precision:

Table 6: System precision table of Motixafortide

S. No	Concentration Motixafortide (µg/ml)	Area of Motixafortide
1.	100	2745862
2.	100	2751230
3.	100	2769693
4.	100	2742103
5.	100	2764110
6.	100	2743287
Mean		2752714
S.D		11565.200
%RSD		0.42

Fig no7 fig no 8 BLANK CHRMATOGRAM

Fig no 9 CHRMATOGRAM OF INTERNAL STANDARD

Fig no 10 CHOMATOGRAM OF MFig: 3 trail 1 of the Motixafortide

TABLE:7 Results of linearity for Motixafortide

S.NO	Motixafortide	
	Conc.($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area
1	25.00	689542
2	50.00	1365487
3	75.00	2035101
4	100.00	2754213
5	125.00	3371201
6	150.00	4117012
Regression equation	$y = 27290.11x + 749.43$	
Slope	27290.11	
Intercept	749.43	
R ²	0.99989	

LINEARITY:

diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide working standard into a 10 ml volumetric flask add

Preparation of Level – I (12.50ppm of Motixafortide):

0.25 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Fig no15 Preparation of Level – II (25.00ppm of Motixaforotide):

0.50 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Fig no 17 Preparation of Level – III (37.50ppm of Motixaforotide):

0.75 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – IV (50.00ppm of Motixaforotide): fig no 14

1.00 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level –V (62.50ppm of Motixafortide): fig 15

1.25 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent

Preparation of Level – VI (75.00ppm of Motixafortide) fig 16

1.50 ml of above stock solutions has taken in different 10 ml of volumetric flasks, dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Fig no17

Procedure:

Inject each level into the UPLC chromatographic system and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

Range:

The Range of an analytical method is the interval between the upper and lower levels of analyte (including these levels) that have been demonstrated with precision, accuracy and linearity

Acceptance Criteria:

Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.999.

Preparation Accuracy Sample solutions:**For preparation of 80% spiking solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10 ml volumetric flask add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1ml of the standard stock solution and 0.8ml of the above sample stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (180ppm of Motixafortide)

For preparation of 100% spiking solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10 ml volumetric flask add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1ml of the standard stock solution and 1ml of the above sample stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (200ppm of Motixafortide)

For preparation of 120% spiking solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10 ml volumetric flask add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1ml of the standard stock solution and 1.2ml of the above sample stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (220ppm of Motixafortide)

Procedure:

Inject the standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions.

Acceptance Criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%

Precision:

Precision is the degree of repeatability of an analytical method under normal operation conditions. Precision is of 3 types

1. System precision
2. Method precision
3. Intermediate precision (a. Intra-day precision, b. Inter day precision)

System precision is checked by using standard chemical substance to ensure that the analytical system is working properly. In this peak area and %

of drug of six determinations is measured and % RSD should be calculated. In method precision, a homogenous sample of single batch should be analyzed 6 times. This indicates whether a method is giving constant results for a single batch. In this analyze the sample six times and calculate the % RSD. The precision of the instrument was checked by repeatedly injecting (n=6) solutions of 100ppm of Motix afortide).

Fig. Inter day precision chromatogram-1 (Day-1)

Fig. 20: Inter day precision chromatogram-2 (Day-1)

Fig.: 22 Inter day precision chromatogram-2 (Day-1)

Fig. 23: Inter day precision chromatogram-4 (Day-1)

Fig. 24 C Inter day precision chromatogram-5 (Day-1)

Inter day precision chromatogram-5 (Day-2) 25

Fig. 26 Inter day precision chromatogram-1 (Day-4) fig 26

Fig. 27: Inter day precision chromatogram-2 (Day-5) fig no27

Fig. 28: Inter day precision chromatogram-3 (Day-2) fig no28

Fig. 29: Inter day precision chromatogram-4 (Day-2)

Inter day precision chromatogram-5 (Day-2) fig no30

Acceptance Criteria:

The % RSD for the area of six replicate injections results should not be more than 2%.

TABLE 8: ROBUSTNESS:

Parameter	Motixafortide					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Tailing	Plate count	%RSD
Flow rate Change (mL/min)	Less flow(0.45ml)	0.819	2574862	1.03	8686	0.55
	Actual flow(0.50ml)	0.693	2745862	0.98	8756	0.42
	More flow(0.55ml)	0.532	2874541	0.92	8831	0.57
Organic Phase change	Less Org (27:73)	0.982	2418795	0.99	8550	0.61
	Actual(30:70)	0.695	2751230	0.95	8720	0.42
	More Org(33:67)	0.405	3023635	0.88	8976	0.46

As part of the Robustness

A. The flow rate was varied at 0.45ml/min to 0.55ml/min.

s, deliberate change in the Flow rate, Mobile Phase composition, Temperature Variation was made to evaluate the impact on the method. Fig no31

Standard solution 100ppm of Motixafortide was prepared and analysed using the varied flow rates along with method flow rate. Fig 32

CHANGE IN FLOW RATE fig bo 33

method is robust even by change in the flow rate $\pm 10\%$.

On evaluation of the above results, it can be concluded that the variation in flow rate affected the method significantly. Hence it indicates that the

B. The variation of Organic Phase ratio.

Fig no 34 Standard solution of 100ppm of Motixafortide was prepared and analysed using the mobile phase ratio. Fig no 37

Fig no 36 LINEARITY GRAPH

Acceptance Criteria:

The % RSD for the area of three standard injections and 3 sample preparation results should not be more than 2%.

The % Assay for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ):

The limit of detection (LOD) limit of quantification (LOQ) of the drug carry was calculated using the following equation as per international conference harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

$$LOQ = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Acceptance Criteria: s/n value for LOD is 3 and LOQ is 19.

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma / S$$

TABLE 9: LOD for Motixafortide was found to be 0.60µg/mL and LOQ for Motixafortide was found to be 2.00g/ml.

Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
80%	4974582	18	18.072	100.4	100.4
	4989203	18	18.125	100.7	
	4960104	18	18.019	100.1	
100%	5554273	20	20.177	100.9	100.7
	5561421	20	20.203	101.0	
	5518950	20	20.049	100.2	
120%	6028741	22	21.901	99.6	99.6
	6042102	22	21.950	99.8	
	6015416	22	21.853	99.3	

Fig no 38 Chromatogram for LOD

Fig no 39

Name of drug	LOD(µg/ml)	s/n	LOQ(µg/ml)	s/n
Motixafortide	0.60	3	2.00	10

DEGRADATION STUDIES:**Acid degradation:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10ml volumetric flask and 1 ml of 1N HCl was added. Then, the volumetric flask was kept

at 60°C for 1 hour and then neutralized with 1 N NaOH and make up to 10ml with diluent. Further dilute 1ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.22 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Alkali degradation: fig no 40

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10ml volumetric flask and 1 ml of 1N NaOH was added. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 1 hour and then neutralized with 1N HCl and make up to 10ml with diluent. Further dilute 1ml

of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.22 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Fig no 41**Peroxide degradation:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10ml volumetric flask, 1 ml of 10 percent w/v hydrogen peroxide was added to the flask and the volume was built up to the mark using diluent.

The vacuum flask was then maintained at 60°C for 1 hour. After that, the vacuum flask was left at room temperature for 15 minutes. Further dilute 1ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution using 0.22 micron syringe filters and transfer to bottles.

Fig no 42

5.7.7.4 Reduction degradation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10ml volumetric flask, 1 ml of 10 percent w/v Sodium bisulphite was added to the flask and the volume was built up to

the mark using diluent. The vacuum flask was then maintained at 60°C for 1 hour. After that, the vacuum flask was left at room temperature for 15 minutes. Further dilute 1ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution using 0.22 micron syringe filters and transfer to bottles.

Fig no 43

Hydrolysis degradation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Motixafortide sample into a 10ml volumetric flask, 1ml of HPLC grade water was added to a flask and the volume was built up to the required volume with diluent. The vacuum flask was then maintained at 60°C for 1 hour.

After that, the vacuum flask was left at room temperature for 15 minutes. Further dilute 1ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution using 0.22 micron syringe filters and transfer to bottles.

Photolytic degradation: fig no 44

Motixafortide sample was placed in Photo stability chamber for 3 hours. Then the exposed sample was taken and diluted with diluents and injected into UPLC and analysed.

Thermal degradation:

Motixafortide standard was taken in petridish and kept in Hot air oven at 105°C for 3 hours. Then the exposed standard was taken and diluted with diluents and injected into UPLC and analysed.

Fig no 45

Acceptance Criteria: Purity threshold is always more than purity angle.

Acknowledgement: All the work done by us with help of staff and students of Nirmala college of pharmacy.

CONCLUSION

The developed UPLC method for the estimation of selected drug is simple, rapid, accurate, precise, robust and economical. The mobile phase and solvents are simple to prepare and economical, reliable, sensitive and less time consuming.

The sample recoveries were in good agreement with their respective label claims and they suggested non interference of formulation excipients in the estimation and can be used in laboratories for the routine analysis of selected drugs. Since the system validation parameters of UPLC method used for estimation of selected drug in pure and have shown satisfactory, accurate and reproducible results (without any interference of excipients) as well, it is deduced that the simple and short proposed methods be most useful for analysis purpose. The present work concluded that stability indicating assay method by UPLC and FD Characterization by using LC-MS/MS was simple, accurate, precise, and specific and has no interference with the placebo and degradation products. Hence these can be used for routine analysis of Motixafortide.

Conflicts of interest: All the authors are equally contributed the work.

REFERENCES

1. Cuatrecasas P, Wilchek M, Anfinsen CB. Selective enzyme purification by affinity chromatography. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1968 Oct;61(2):636-43.
2. Porath J. From gel filtration to adsorptive size exclusion. *Journal of protein chemistry*. 1997 Jul;16(5):463-8.
3. Harris DC. *Exploring chemical analysis*. 3rd ed, WH. Freeman&Co 2004
4. Khan H, Ali J. UHPLC: Applications in pharmaceutical analysis. *Asian J. Pharm. Ana*. 2017 May;7(2):124-31.
5. Chesnut SM, Salisbury JJ. The role of UHPLC in pharmaceutical development. *Journal of separation science*. 2007 May;30(8):1183-90.
6. Fallas MM, Neue UD, Hadley MR, McCalley DV. Further investigations of the effect of pressure on retention in ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography. *Journal of Chromatography A*. 2010 Jan 15;1217(3):276-84.
7. Nguyen DT, Guillaume D, Heinisch S, Barrioulet MP, Rocca JL, Rudaz S, Veuthey JL. High throughput liquid chromatography with sub-2 µm particles at high pressure and high temperature. *Journal of Chromatography A*. 2007 Oct 5;1167(1):76-84.
8. Nguyen DT, Guillaume D, Rudaz S, Veuthey JL. Fast analysis in liquid chromatography using small particle size and high pressure. *Journal of separation science*. 2006 Aug;29(12):1836-48.
9. Swartz ME. Ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC): An introduction. *Separation Science Re-Defined, LCGC Supplement*. 2005 May 1;8:8-14.
10. Beattie I, Joncour K, Lawson K. Ultra performance liquid chromatography coupled to orthogonal quadrupole TOF-MS (MS) for metabolite identification. *LC-GC North America*. 2005 May 1;23(5):S22-.
11. Wang W, Wang S, Tan S, Wen M, Qian Y, Zeng X, Guo Y, Yu C. Detection of urine metabolites in polycystic ovary syndrome by UPLC triple-TOF-MS. *Clinica Chimica Acta*. 2015 Aug 25;448:39-47.
12. Neumeyer, David. *Guide to Schenkerian Analysis*. The University of Texas at Austin; University of Texas Libraries. November 2018.
13. Ziaei-Moayyed, Maryam; Goodman, Edward; Williams, Peter. "Electrical Deflection of Polar Liquid Streams: A Misunderstood Demonstration". *Journal of Chemical Education*. 2000, 77 (11): 1520.
14. S. A. Benner; K. G. Devine; L. N. Matveeva; D. H. Powell (2000). "The missing organic molecules on Mars". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 97 (6): 2425–2430.
15. Verbeck G, Hoffmann W, Walton B. "Soft-landing preparative mass spectrometry". *The Analyst*. October 2012, 137 (19): 4393–407.
16. Shevela D, Messinger J. Studying the oxidation of water to molecular oxygen in photosynthetic and

- artificial systems by time-resolved membrane-inlet mass spectrometry. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, November 2013, 4: 473.
17. Iwata, Kota; Yamazaki, Shiro; Mutombo, Pingo; Hapala, Prokop; Ondráček, Martin; Jelínek, Pavel; Sugimoto, Yoshiaki (2015). "Chemical structure imaging of a single molecule by atomic force microscopy at room temperature". *Nature Communications*. 6: 7766.
 18. Padmavathi sakinala, G.Saisreelakshmi, N. Haritha yadav, RP- HPLC method development validation and stability studies of olanzapine and semidorphan in combined dosage form, *Journal of pharmaceutical and negative result*. May 2023
 19. Sk. Abdul Rahaman, padmavathi sakinala, N.Khaleel, Method development and validation of residual solvents in pyroxetine by gas chromatography. May 2022
 20. Rp-Hplc Method Development, Validation And Stability Studies Of Olanzapine And Samidorphan In Combined Dosage Forms
 21. K Rajiya Sulthana . padmavathi Sakinala , Sucharitha kuppala, pamidiboyina sri pujitha , L.P. Vistaja Singamsetty , Chemometric assisted new stability indicating NP-HPLC method development and validation of clavulanic acid , amoxicillne and lactobacillus in combined dosage form. *journal of cardiovascular disease and research*, vol12,issue5, 2021

HOW TO CITE: S. Padmavathi, Pulagani Triveni, UPLC Method Development, Validation & Degradation Studies of Motixafortide Tablet dosage forms, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (2), 148-172. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18595088>

